

Comparison of Three Methods for Quadratic Potential Propagators Part III

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Mar. 18, 2021

In a previous note (Part II), we considered three different approaches to calculating the propagator for the Schrodinger equation: $i\hbar \frac{d}{dt} W = -\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} + k(t)x^2 + f(t)x$ (1). The first postulated the form $Q(t)\exp\{-i[b(t)XX + g(t)YY + g_2(t)XY]\}$, substituted it into the Schrodinger equation and equates coefficients of XX , YY , XY separately (1). The other two methods (2),(3) linked the propagator to a classical Lagrangian. Method (2) used only classical solutions of the Lagrangian, while (3) postulated the form $Q(t)\exp(-i \text{Action})$ for the propagator. (These approaches are applied to Lagrangians which are quadratic in X .)

It was noted in (2), that $f(t) x \frac{dx}{dt}$ may be written classically as: $\frac{d}{dt} [0.5xx f(t)] - 0.5xx \frac{df}{dt}$. The term $\frac{d}{dt} [0.5xx f(t)]$ contributes nothing to the classical equations of motion and so is dropped. Method (3) does not drop such a term as the propagator is $\exp(-i\text{Action})$ leading to an additional phase $\exp(-i \int dt \frac{d}{dt} [0.5xx f(t)])$. Furthermore, even with this extra phase, $\exp(-i \text{Action})$ does not satisfy the time dependent Schrodinger equation.

In this note, we wish to examine why there seem to be issues with removing a $\frac{d}{dt} [0.5xx f(t)]$ piece from a Lagrangian when calculating a quantum propagator. We argue that a propagator linked to a classical Lagrangian i.e. $\exp(-i\text{Action})$ for a free particle and a spring with $k(t)$ as the spring constant leads to a coefficient of $c \frac{dA}{dt} / A$ where A is a solution of the classical equations of motion. This behaviour is consistent with a fluctuation equation linking $\frac{d}{dt}$ with $\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx}$ and $V(x, \frac{dx}{dt})$ the potential i.e. the Schrodinger equation. Thus, we argue that the Schrodinger equation propagator is linked to classical equations of motion, but only for certain cases which produce a special kind of fluctuation. We argue that the extra phase $\exp(-i \int dt \frac{d}{dt} [0.5xx f(t)])$ does not satisfy this fluctuation rule.

To clarify, we consider the free particle case, add a potential $\frac{d}{dt} [0.5xx f(t)]$ and argue that the phase $\exp(-i \int dt \frac{d}{dt} [0.5xx f(t)])$ multiplied by $\exp(ipx - iEt)$ is a solution only if $x(t)$ is taken to be classical within the phase integral. This is not a quantum mechanical solution as it only considers classical motion and leads to a kind of hybrid equation mixing quantum fluctuations with a classical phase. Thus, it seems one must be careful when linking classical physics (i.e. the Lagrangian) to the Schrodinger equation.

$\frac{d}{dt} [0.5xx f(t)]$ Potentials

The potential $\frac{d}{dt} [0.5xx f(t)]$, when added to a Lagrangian does not affect the classical equations of motion. From the point of view of classical physics which deals with accelerations, such a potential may be dropped as done in (2). In quantum mechanics, which seems to be a fluctuation theory, a potential may lead to a phase without leading to acceleration as in the Bohm Aharonov case for which there is a particle with fixed momentum. If a quantum particle may have a potential which does not change the equation of motion, one may think that $\frac{d}{dt} [0.5xx f(t)]$ expanded as $\frac{df}{dt} 0.5xx + f x \frac{dx}{dt}$ may be used in the time-dependent Schrodinger

equation yielding a phase $\exp(-i \int dx f(x))$ which is consistent with the approach of (3) i.e. $Q(x)\exp(-i \text{Action})$ as the propagator.

We find, however, that such an approach is inconsistent with the Schrodinger equation:

$$i \frac{d}{dt} W = -\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} + k(x) + f(x) \frac{d}{dx} W \quad ((1))$$

One may use $Q(x)\exp\{-i [b(x)XX + g(t)YY + g^2(t)XY]\}$ ((2)) as the propagator and obtain the following equation for $b(x)$, the coefficient of XX :

$$2b \frac{db}{dx} = \frac{4}{2m} (bb + k(x) + f(x) 2b) \quad ((3))$$

If $f(x)$ is zero, then $Q(x)\exp(-i \text{Action})$ and ((2)) inserted into the time-dependent Schrodinger equation yield the same value for $b(x)$ namely constant $dA/dt / A$. Given that:

$$f(x) \frac{dx}{dt} = \frac{d}{dt} [\int dx f] - \int dx \frac{df}{dt} \quad ((4))$$

one might consider ((1)) with $k_1(x) = \{ k(x) - \int dx \frac{df}{dt} \}$ and the additional potential $\int dx f$.

$\int dx f$ does not affect the classical equation of motion, thus one might expect to see a solution with a phase such as $\exp(-i \int dt \frac{d}{dt} [\int dx f]) = \exp(-i \int dx f)$ following the $\exp(-i \text{Action})$ method. This, however, does not appear to be the case. If one considers $b_0(x)$ to be the coefficient of XX in ((2)) for $k_1(x) = \{ k(x) - \int dx \frac{df}{dt} \}$ and alters this to include the phase $\int dx f$:

$$b(x) = b_0(x) + \int dx f \quad ((5))$$

((5)) is not a solution of ((3)) i.e.

$$2b \frac{db}{dx} + \int dx f \frac{df}{dx} \neq \frac{4}{2m} (b_0^2 + \int dx f + b_0 \int dx f) + k_1(x) + \int dx f \frac{d}{dx} (b_0 + \int dx f) \quad ((6))$$

Where $b_0 = c_1 \frac{dA}{dt} / A$ and $m \frac{d}{dt} \frac{dA}{dt} = -k_1(x)$ such that:

$$2b \frac{db}{dx} = \frac{2}{2m} b_0^2 + k(x) \quad \text{i.e. } c_1 = -1/2m \quad \text{Let us set } m=1$$

Then ((6)) reduces to:

$$\int dx f \frac{df}{dx} \neq \frac{4}{2} (\int dx f - \int dx f) + \int dx f \frac{df}{dx} + \int dx f - \int dx f \frac{dA}{dt} / A \quad ((7))$$

The $\int dx f$ terms do not cancel and so ((7)) is not an equation and one does not have a phase adjustment i.e. ((5)) satisfying the time-dependent Schrodinger equation.

This seems to suggest that it is not enough to have a quadratic Lagrangian, rather there seems to be a certain fluctuation rule applied as one changes X and T independently in order to obtain the time-Schrodinger equation. In particular, in (3), the classical solution is written as:

$$x(t) = X \frac{A(T_f - t)}{A(T)} + Y \frac{A(t - T_0)}{A(T)} \quad ((8))$$

Here X is the initial point, Y the endpoint and $T = T_f - T_0$. In obtaining a time-dependent Schrodinger equation, X and T are changed independently with the constraint that $i\hbar \frac{d}{dt}$ changes to a function $\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d^2}{dx^2} + V(x, dx/dt)$ changes. This holds for both a free propagator and oscillator with a $k(t)$ spring constant and leads to $b(t) = \text{constant} \frac{dA/dt}{A}$ where $A(t)$ is a solution of the classical equation of motion. Simply adding a phase to $\frac{dA/dt}{A}$ i.e. $\frac{1}{2} \int f(t) dx$ as done above does not maintain a form consistent with the fluctuation rule. It may be noted that in classical physics, one would not alter X and T independently. They are linked. If $T_i = 0$ and $Y = 0$ at T_f , then $T = T_f$ and $X = -vT$ where v is the velocity. Thus, it seems that changing these independently with the $\frac{d}{dt}$, $\frac{d}{dx}$ rule imposes a special kind of fluctuation rule i.e. time-dependent quantum mechanics.

We next consider the case of a free propagator with the potential $\frac{d}{dt} [\frac{1}{2} \int f]$ to try to see further what is occurring.

Free Propagator with the Potential $\frac{d}{dt} [\frac{1}{2} \int f]$

It is possible to create a free particle propagator using $\exp(-i \text{Action})$ and using:

$$x(t) = X \frac{v(T_f - t)}{vT} + Y \frac{v(t - T_i)}{vT} \text{ where } v \text{ is the velocity. } ((9))$$

If $T_i = 0$ and $T_f = T$, then $x(t) = X \frac{(T-t)}{T} + Y \frac{t}{T}$. To simplify further, let $Y = 0$ so $x(t) = X \frac{(T-t)}{T}$.

The Lagrangian is: $\frac{m}{2} \frac{dx}{dt} \frac{dx}{dt} \quad ((10)) = \frac{m}{2} \left(\frac{XX}{TT} \right)$ and the action $\frac{m}{2} \frac{XX}{TT} T = \frac{m}{2} \frac{XX}{T}$.

Thus, the factor of $b(t)XX$ in the action is: $(\frac{1}{2m}) (\frac{1}{T}) = (\frac{1}{2m}) (\frac{v}{vT})$ or $(\frac{1}{2m}) \frac{dA/dt}{A}$ evaluated at T. This is a special form consistent with $i\hbar \frac{d}{dt}$ of a function (namely $\exp(-i \text{Action})$) matching $-\frac{1}{2} \frac{d^2}{dx^2}$ of the same function.

It is possible to add the potential $\frac{d}{dt} [\frac{1}{2} \int f(t)] = \frac{df}{dt} \cdot \frac{1}{2} \int f + f \frac{dx}{dt}$ to the Lagrangian ((10)) without changing the equation of motion i.e. $\frac{dx}{dt} = \text{constant}$.

In such a case, one obtains a phase for $\exp(-i \text{Action})$ namely $\exp(- \text{free propagator} + \frac{1}{2} \int f(t))$ ((11)). Note $A(0) = 0$ and free propagator = $\frac{1}{2m} \frac{XX}{T}$

Inserting this into the time-dependent Schrodinger equation, however, leads to problems:

$$i\hbar \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{1}{2m} \frac{1}{T} + \frac{1}{2} \int f(t) \right) \text{ not} = \frac{1}{2m} \left(\frac{1}{2m} \frac{1}{T} + \frac{1}{2} \int f \right) \left(\frac{1}{2m} \frac{1}{T} + \frac{1}{2} \int f \right) + \frac{df}{dt} \cdot \frac{1}{2} \int f + f^2 \left(\frac{1}{2m} \frac{1}{T} + \frac{1}{2} \int f \right) \quad ((12)) \text{ Set } m=1$$

One may see that $\psi\psi$ terms again do not cancel: $\frac{1}{2} \psi$ and $\psi\psi$. Thus, something strange seems to be occurring.

To examine this more closely, one may consider a solution of the Schrodinger equation as:

$$W(x,t) = \exp(ipx - iEt) \exp(-i \int_0^t dt' \frac{d}{dt'} [\frac{1}{2} \psi\psi]) \quad ((13))$$

$$\frac{d}{dt} [\frac{1}{2} \psi\psi] = \text{potential} = \frac{1}{2} \psi\psi \frac{df}{dt} + f \frac{dx}{dt}$$

The time-dependent Schrodinger equation is:

$$i \frac{d}{dt} W = -\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W + \frac{1}{2} \psi\psi \frac{df}{dt} + f (-i \frac{d}{dx}) W$$

If the phase (second factor in ((13))) is considered to be a function of time, then:

$$i \frac{d}{dt} W = -\frac{1}{2m} p^2 + \frac{1}{2} \psi\psi \frac{df}{dt} + f p$$

$$\text{And} \quad i \frac{d}{dt} W = E + \frac{1}{2} \psi(t)\psi(t) \frac{df}{dt} + f \frac{dx}{dt}$$

with $\frac{dx}{dt}=p$ for $m=1$. Thus, there is a way to allow for the phase in ((13)) to be part of a solution of the Schrodinger equation, but there are two problems:

((1)) One uses $x(t)$ in the phase which is purely classical in the phase. Once the time derivative is taken $x(t)$ which was a pure time function immediately becomes X .

((2)) One does not write $x(t)$ in terms of X and T which are considered to be fluctuating.

Thus, ((13)) creates a hybrid i.e. a combination of a quantum result which allows for $i \frac{d}{dT}$ fluctuations to balance with $-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dX} \frac{d}{dX}$, but then uses a purely classical phase to try to cancel out a potential term. In other words, there do not seem to be any "special" quantum fluctuations associated with the extra phase even though it may be used in such a manner to cancel off the "fictitious" potential pieces.

Thus, it seems one must be careful when associating quantum mechanics with classical Lagrangians. Quantum mechanics seems to be associated with special types of fluctuations of X and T i.e. $i \frac{d}{dT}$ and $-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dX} \frac{d}{dX} + V$ balances. Classically, one would not vary X and T independently even with such a balance. Thus, one cannot necessarily consider adding a phase to account for a classical potential which does not affect the equation of motions. Such a phase only cancels the non-accelerating potential if one ignores fluctuations and treats $x(t)$ as a classical quantity in the phase, but then matches this to potential also written classically. This, however, would lead to a hybrid quantum-fluctuation/ classical equation.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we examine the addition of a $d/dt [L_{\text{extra}} f(t)]$ potential to a classical Lagrangian which does not change the classical equations of motion. If one tries to account for this by adding a phase i.e. $\exp(-i \int L_{\text{extra}} dt)$ where $L_{\text{extra}} = d/dt [L_{\text{extra}} f(t)]$, this phase only cancels the potential in the time-dependent Schrodinger equation if one treats $x(t)$ as a classical pure time function when applying $i d/dt$. As soon as a time derivative is taken, $x(t)$ is treated as X , independent of T . This, however, violates the entire idea of taking a classical Lagrangian and varying X and T independently (i.e. introducing fluctuations it seems) to obtain a differential equation with a special fluctuation rule namely that $i d/dT$ balances $-1/2m d/dX d/dX + V$. This "special" fluctuation equation is the time-dependent Schrodinger equation.

Thus, one must be careful when linking quantum mechanics to classical mechanics and manipulating the potential in the Lagrangian. In classical mechanics, removing a piece of potential which does not alter the classical equations of motion is fine. In quantum mechanics, it is not because such a potential may lead to a phase change as in the Bohm Aharonov case. Furthermore, this phase change must be in keeping with the fluctuation ideas of quantum mechanics. One may not use $\exp(-i \text{Action})$ and create an extra phase which is not in keeping with X , T fluctuations such that there is a balance between $i d/dT$ and $-1/2m d/dX d/dX + V$.

References

1. Cordero-Soto, R. and Lopez, R. and Suazo, E. and Suslov, S. Propagator of a Charged Particle with a Spin in Uniform Magnetic and Perpendicular Electric Fields (2008)
<https://arxiv.org/pdf/0801.3246.pdf>
2. Keirandish, F. A novel derivation of quantum propagator for time-dependent trapping and control (2018)
<https://arxiv.org/pdf/1612.07674.pdf>
3. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Path_integral_formulation#Free_particle